

ACYL KETENES AND THEIR POLYMERISATION

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Reactions expected to give 2,4-diacetylcyclobutane-1,3-dione (I) gave actually compounds of the class of dehydracetic acid (II). It is suggested that transformation of (I) into (II) takes place through acyl ketene as an intermediate.

By allowing ketene to polymerise at low temperature Chick and Willsmore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 946) obtained a brown solid and a liquid in poor yield. The latter on fractionation boiled at 125°-127° and was found to consist of a compound C₄H₄O₂ (M. W. 84) which, from its properties, was regarded by them to be acetylketene (I)

The isomeric cyclobutane-1:3-dione structure (II) was not preferred on ground of physical properties and of the fact that with phenylhydrazine the product obtained was phenylhydrazino-phenylhydrazide (III) instead of the diphenylhydrazone of the diketone (II).

Staudinger and Bereza (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4908) from the study of a disubstituted ketene, which they were investigating and which according to them polymerised to the corresponding cyclobutane-1:3-dione, suggested that Chick and Willsmore's 'acetylketene' was really cyclobutane-1:3-dione (II). The acetylketene structure was according to them further untenable on the ground that the compound, unlike ketene, was stable and did not add alcohol.

Chick and Willsmore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1978) in reply pointed out that in presence of a trace of mineral acid their compound gradually added alcohol and formed acetoacetic ester and that on prolonged standing in presence of alcohol, dehydracetic acid (IV) was the final product.

Since, however, the compound added bromine to form γ -bromoacetoacetyl bromide (V) and not the α -bromo compound (VI)

they modified their original view and accepted Staudinger and Bereza's *cyclobutane-1:3-dion* structure for their compound. They admitted that "the true acetylketene has therefore yet to be discovered, and when discovered it will resemble *cyclobutane-1:3-dion* in its reactions."

Billore, Nigam, Kaushal and Deshapande (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 19) attempted the synthesis of *2:4-diacetylcyclobutane-1:3-dion* (VIII) by treating copper salt of diacetylacetone (VII) with carbonyl chloride in benzene.

They obtained, however, a product which from its properties and analysis was identified by them as dehydracetic acid (IV). They suggested that on account of the instability of the structure (VIII) (cf. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 305) fission took place into two molecules of acetylketene (I) which then recombined to form the more stable six-ring structure of dehydracetic acid.

The present work was undertaken to see whether more instances of this kind of transformation could be collected.

When the copper salt of dipropionyl acetone (IX, R=Et) (Deshapande, Dingankar and Kokil, this *Journal*, 1934, 10, 595) was treated in benzene suspension with carbonyl chloride, dissolved in benzene, the sole product of the reaction was identified as dehydro-

propionylacetic acid (X, R=Et) (Pechmann and Neger, *Annalen*, 1893, 278, 86; Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1932, 8, 303)

The copper salt of di-*n*-butyrylacetone (IX, R=C₃H₇) (Deshapande, Diugankar and Kokil, *loc. cit.*) under similar conditions gave dehydrobutyrylacetic acid (X, R=C₃H₇) (Deshapande, *loc. cit.*).

It seems from the cases so far studied that when a reaction is expected to yield 2 : 4-diacylcyclobutane-1 : 3-dion, the compound actually formed belongs to the class of dehydracetic acid. The intermediate formation of an acylketene and its polymerisation to more stable six-ring structure is the mechanism suggested. The replacement of acyl by alkyl groups in 2 : 4-positions of cyclobutane-1 : 3-dion precludes the possibility of transformation of four-ring into six-ring in the manner suggested above. Thus, 2 : 4-dimethylcyclobutane-1 : 3-dion, obtained by decarboxylation of the 4-carboxylic acid (Schroter, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1607), is quite stable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Salt of Dipropionylacetone.—Dipropionylacetone (prepared from 2 : 6-diethyl-4-pyrone by fission with barium hydroxide followed by acidification) was dissolved in alcohol. Cold saturated solution of sodium acetate and copper acetate was added to it when the green copper salt was precipitated which was washed free of copper acetate and was dried at 100°, yield almost the theoretical.

Reaction with Carbonyl Chloride.—To the suspension of the dry copper salt (5.7 g., 1 mol.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) was added, under cooling, a solution of carbonyl chloride (2.6 g., 1 mol., liquefied at 0°), dissolved in benzene (18 c.c.). The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 5 hours with occasional shaking; it was then allowed to remain at room temperature for five days for the reaction to complete. The deep brown benzene layer was filtered off from copper chloride, washed with water, dried and the solvent allowed to evaporate. The crystalline mass obtained was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol in needles, m.p. 71° (mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of dehydropropionylacetic acid, prepared from dehydropropionylacetocarboxylic acid, 71°; Pechmann and Neger, *loc. cit.*), yield 2.5 g.

The copper salt of di-*n*-butyrylacetone was prepared from the ketone and was treated with carbonyl chloride in the same manner as the copper salt of the lower homologue. The copper salt (7.5 g.) and carbonyl chloride (2.9 g.) were used. The red benzene layer after completion of the reaction was filtered from copper chloride, washed with water and extracted with caustic soda. On acidifying the aqueous layer, a liquid separated which was extracted with ether. On washing and drying the ethereal extract

and removing the solvent, a liquid with acid reactions remained (yield 3 g.). After cooling by ice the liquid solidified. The solid, freed from little adhering liquid by draining, melted at 16° (dehydrobutyrylacetic acid freezes at 16°). As mixed melting point observations at such low temperature are not convincing, confirmation of the identity of the acid with dehydrobutyrylacetic acid was obtained by determination of its equivalent weight. (Found. Equiv., 227 $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$ requires equiv., 224)

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